

MEANING OF EDUCATION MANAGEMENT AND EVOLUTION OF MANAGEMENT CONCEPTS IN EDUCATION

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Quality management systems of university activities, regardless of the specifics of the mechanisms, procedures and forms used, as a rule, have all the system attributes: the purpose of functioning, processes, implementation algorithm, quality (result efficiency), means of its organizational and technical and technological support (implementation conditions: structure, material and technical base, educational and methodological support, technologies and teaching methods, etc.).

As a consequence of the high level of competition and the development of globalization processes, the systems for managing university activities abroad have a strategic focus. Strategic quality management in higher education in the countries of the post-Soviet space is at an early stage of development.

ABSTRACT

Higher education of the 21st century is distinguished by a number of features and requires certain changes in the content and organization of education. One of the objectively existing factors stimulating changes in the system of higher education is the rapidly increasing flow of information. This growth is happening at such a pace that the old methods of communication and the education system itself can no longer cope with it.

An important aspect of strategic management is the choice of a quality management system model. An analysis of the concept and program for the development of domestic education indicates that the education system is characterized by the commitment of the quality management system to the principles of the model of the European education system. This explains the existence of a clearly traceable trend in the formation of a national model of education, taking into account the principles of the quality standards. Depending on the degree of involvement of universities in this process, this, to a greater or lesser extent, is reflected in the structure and content of quality management systems for university activities. From the point of view of the structure, this fact is explained by the

existence within the framework of the credit technology of a number of new structural formations involved in quality management (office registrar service, adviser service, resource committee, and a number of others), and from the point of view of content, by the specifics of the content of the credit technology itself. and the associated specifics of the forms and methods of teaching and assessment of knowledge, on the one hand, and the revision, taking into account foreign experience, of the system of indicators of national assessment procedures, on the other.

The scientific literature contains many formulations of the concept of "system". At the same time, two main approaches to its formation are distinguished: 1) an indication of its integrity as an essential feature of any system; 2) understanding of the system as a set of elements together with the relationships between them.

The system is understood as "the purposeful integrity of interconnected elements, which has new integrative properties that are absent from each of them, associated with the external environment."

Pedagogical systems are distinguished among many types of social systems. According to their characteristics, pedagogical systems are real (by origin), social (by substantive), complex (by the level of complexity), open (by the nature of interaction with the external environment), dynamic (by the basis of variability), probabilistic (by the method of determination), purposeful (by the presence of goals), self-governing (by the basis of controllability) character. Under the condition of purposefulness and dynamism, they still have developing

properties, which is manifested in their constant variability. Pedagogical systems are open, because information processes take place between them and the surrounding reality.

Many prominent scientists have devoted their works to a systematic approach, in which, to varying degrees of completeness, such a phenomenon as the pedagogical system is considered. Different authors give the following formulations of the concept of "system":

- 1) a set of interrelated components that make up a certain whole in their structure and functioning;
- 2) A certain community of elements that function according to its inherent goals;
- 3) An ordered set of interrelated elements identified on the basis of certain characteristics, united by a common goal of functioning and unity of control and acting in interaction with the environment as an integral unity. As a pedagogical system, both the educational process and the means, methods, organizational forms of education are considered;
- 4) Any process taking place under certain conditions, in conjunction with these conditions. Systems in which pedagogical processes take place are defined as pedagogical systems that have certain elements or objects and their relationships or structures and functions. A university, a technical school, etc., can act as a system, which include administrative, economic, and other subsystems. But the leading element in them is the pedagogical subsystem, which is also a system at the same time. The pedagogical system, like any other system, has its own structure (didactic task, teaching technology, public order, subjects of the educational process). Also, the pedagogical system is understood

as a certain set of interrelated means, methods, processes necessary to create an organized, purposeful and deliberate pedagogical influence on the formation of a personality with given qualities.

The pedagogical system is "a socially conditioned integrity of the participants in the pedagogical process interacting on the basis of cooperation between themselves, the environment and its spiritual and material values, aimed at the formation and development of the individual." This is "a relatively stable set of elements, an organizational connection of people, their spheres of action, the order in which functions are performed, spatial and temporal connections, relationships, methods of interaction and the structure of activities in the interests of achieving certain educational goals and results, solving the planned cultural and developmental tasks of upbringing and human learning."

Within the framework of a systematic approach, an educational institution is considered as a complex socio-pedagogical system, i.e., as a set of interconnected elements. It includes a wide variety of educational systems. Thus, a holistic pedagogical (educational) process is a system. The learning process, being a subsystem of a holistic educational process, is also considered as an educational system. A training session is a subsystem of the learning process and, in turn, is a complex educational system.

Each individual pedagogical system (in particular, the university as an educational system) is complex because it itself has subsystems in the form of groups, classes, etc., but this system itself is included as a subsystem in the education system.

The pedagogical system of a relatively closed type is characterized by a clearly defined internal structure, often hierarchical; it is built according to certain rules, and the individual submits to the group in it. On the contrary, an open pedagogical system is characterized by a high degree of individualism, a minimum of the desire of team members to maintain both internal and external boundaries.

The functioning, development and self-development of the educational process as a pedagogical system is the main condition for its existence. Development and self-development are basically a real means of functioning, that is, in a broad sense, a consequence of purposeful activity. For example, the development of any person is a consequence of his activity and communication. Any educational system is created with the aim of ensuring the development of the growth of a qualitative change in students, primarily on the basis of their interactions with the teacher, with each other, with a textbook, with a computer, and so on.

It is known that the elements of any pedagogical system can be systems of lower orders. The educational process as a system is characterized by the presence of relations between its objects and between their properties.

The structure, or organization, of a system is the most important condition for its existence and an equally necessary feature. This provision relates to the educational process as a pedagogical system in the most direct way, since it is meaningless to talk about its existence without the interaction of real people, in the real conditions of a secondary educational institution, training sessions, and the like.

The educational process as a system has specific goals, functions and properties that differ from the goals, functions and properties of its constituent objects, relationships and attributes. The objects of any system are simply its parts, components, and attributes are the properties of the objects of the system. Relationships are the means by which the system is united into one whole, in our case, it is the interaction of the subjects of the educational process as a whole.

The presence of two or more types of communication is also the most important feature, characteristic, condition for the existence of the educational process as an active system.

Integrity is the most important condition for the existence of the educational process as a pedagogical system, its main property and main feature. Violation of integrity leads to the disintegration of the activity system as such. The property of integrity determines the relationship, mutual influence, mutual development of all components and system-forming factors of the pedagogical system as a whole.

Thus, the educational process, as an active system, is constantly in continuous development, having a colossal ability to improve under the condition of a clear, scientific organization of its management, and vice versa, it shows a tendency to degradation in the absence or poor organization of management of this process. In principle, no person can be taught anything if he himself does not want to. To manage the cognitive and self-educational process means, first of all, to direct, help, correct on the basis of a clear planning of the organization and control of the process as a whole.

Fundamental changes in the socio-economic life and the state-political structure of the Russian Federation have necessitated an education reform. During the first stage of its implementation, the domestic education system freed itself from the legacy of totalitarianism, became more open, democratic and diverse.

However, the implementation of educational reform was held back by the difficulties of the transition period. These difficulties are caused both by the reduction in production volumes and national income, which made the temporary reduction in budgetary financing of education inevitable, and by the delay in creating a new organizational and economic mechanism for the educational sphere itself. These reasons led to the unsatisfactory state of the material base of educational institutions, led to delays in the payment of the teaching staff, and affected the organization and quality of the educational process. Financial stabilization and a trend towards economic growth make it possible not only to overcome the emerging difficulties, but also to begin a new stage in reforming the education system.

At the new stage, profound changes are envisaged in the activities of educational institutions. The content and structure of the education system needs to be radically updated. It is necessary to create conditions for the development of scientific research, strengthen the system of social guarantees provided to the personnel of educational institutions, and ensure the improvement of the health of students. One of the key aspects of the reform is the creation of a new organizational and economic mechanism that meets the conditions of a modern market economy

and is designed to ensure the attraction and rational use of resources necessary for the development of education.

The purpose of the reform is to reliably guarantee the constitutional rights, freedoms and interests of citizens in the educational sphere, to bring the education system in line with the modern needs of the individual, society and the state, to create prerequisites for its further development, increase in achievements and preservation of the best traditions based on a combination of state, public and private initiatives, to significantly improve the preparation of new generations for life and work in a democratic civil society with a market economy.

The reform of education is aimed at achieving this goal as a set of state policy measures provided by financial, economic, organizational, administrative, recommendatory and information methods.

The new stage of the reform will be implemented on the organizational basis of the Federal Program for the Development of Education, coordinated by the Ministry of Education, regional, local and departmental education authorities with active and largely independent actions of the teaching staff of educational institutions of all types, trustees and parental councils of educational institutions. Private and public initiatives, as well as the support of families and employers, interested business, state-political and other public circles, are called upon to play a huge role in the reform.

As a result of reforming the education system, it is planned to quickly eliminate the prerequisites for social tension in educational institutions, normalize their funding, create conditions for improving

the organization and quality of the educational process. This will make possible a phased transition to solving increasingly complex economic and social problems of the development of the educational sphere so that Russia enters the 21st century with the necessary conditions for the growth of the education of the population, its cultural level, the training of qualified personnel for all sectors of the economy and the social sphere, increasing the scientific potential of the country.

In the 21st century, a change in the educational paradigm is taking place: a variable content of education and pedagogical technologies, new modern pedagogical concepts and ideas are offered. The content of education is saturated with various educational programs that contribute to the development of students' skills and abilities to operate with information, to solve problems creatively. The use of computer teaching aids, telecommunication networks of a global scale is changing the traditional ways of information. A feature of the educational process is the orientation towards personality-oriented learning, the formation and development of the spiritual and moral sphere of a person. The value orientations in education are the personality of the student, his ability for independent activity in collecting, processing and analyzing information, the ability to make decisions and apply the knowledge gained in life. The tasks of the teacher also become different: "Not to teach, but to induce, not to evaluate, but to analyze." The teacher in relation to the student ceases to be a source of information, but becomes a source of spiritual and intellectual impulse that

encourages action "(Peterson L.G.). The role of science in the creation of pedagogical technologies that are adequate to the level of public knowledge is growing. The integration of the school, family, micro- and macro-society is increasing. Under these conditions, the development of the teacher's professional skills, his creative abilities, which make it possible to effectively carry out methodological activities in changing pedagogical conditions and in relation to various situations, acquires particularly relevant importance.

In real pedagogical practice, this transition is not carried out professionally enough, contradictory, more often in the absence of a system of preparation for such activities, which must be carried out through a series of scientific, methodological consultations and events, where the teacher's leading guides to changing the learning process should become methodological centers, institutions for the development of education and, first of all, a methodologist. The difficulties of a teacher in professional practice are the result of a number of circumstances: on the one hand, they are largely due to the traditionally established system of methodological preparation of a teacher for methodological activity, which, as a rule, does not provide for the relationship between science and practices; ignoring the real needs and social order of society and the personality of the child. On the other hand, the lack of knowledge and skills of the methodologist (by position); the lack of development of mechanisms for including a teacher in the design of a modern educational process does not contribute to the development of a need for teachers to improve their own methodological professionalism:

The country does not have, as such, a system of higher professional training for educators of methodological centers. The pedagogical staff of the municipal education system for methodological offices is usually made up of teachers who have gone through the natural path of their own professionalization. The lack of a scientific base of methodological and methodological knowledge on the modern psychological and pedagogical training of teachers does not allow methodological services to quickly master new areas of theory and practice in the field of education.

In modern conditions, the educational theme is territorial, taking into account all the connections within a given territorial entity. The deteriorating economic situation does not contribute to maintaining the education system only from the center, and in the process of municipalization of education, its problems are solved at the local level and only when high levels can no longer help. The development of information links, the transition to cooperative and coordinating links that ensure a guaranteed high quality of the education process, is the essence of the process of municipalization of the education system

These processes influence the emergence of aspects of methodological activity in educational institutions and educational systems of the district and city, namely the creation of a system of organizational and pedagogical activities that provides a set of socially oriented measures aimed at meeting the educational needs of the individual and society.

In the conditions of municipalization of education, municipal methodological centers are forced to study regional and

municipal features, ethnographic, historical, cultural, modern, socio-economic conditions in the region, district, city; trends and prospects for its development, etc.) and focus on them in the content and organization of educational processes. The municipalization of education in this case is considered as a process of ensuring the completeness, continuity of the process of education of a particular child living in a given territory. The possibility of completeness and continuity of the process of education of the younger generation is approved by the system of educational structures of the region, city, district, which together form a complete cycle of educational activities. At the same time, the municipal education system needs to take into account the educational needs of the local community to the maximum extent possible. It should focus on the current and future needs of the local labor market, maintain and develop local historical and cultural traditions, ways of social and family life, build its activities taking into account local educational traditions.

In this case, the activities of methodological services are implemented through the diversity of educational opportunities of the modern municipal education system, which acquires national features, taking into account the peculiarities of the socio-economic development of a particular territory, its cultural and everyday roots. And this means that methodologists and practicing teachers will have to work in a diverse and developing educational system. Accounting for local characteristics, the socio-cultural environment in the teacher training system will create a reliable basis for the reorganization and development of the education system as social needs and

municipal requirements change. Here it becomes obvious that the quality of the professional methodological activity of pedagogical workers is determined not so much by the current level of professional training, but by the ability to adapt to activities to solve emerging problems.

Modern approaches to the methodological activities of municipal methodological services are manifested in the actualization of the productive use of methods, forms and content of methodological work, in active participation in innovative activities and creative projects, in the ability to develop and implement new educational programs and pedagogical technologies.

Systematic training in the methodology of scientific research of topical and underdeveloped problems should orient the methodologist not to relaying, but to research, design functions. Practice shows that the work of methodologists with teachers is traditionally carried out mainly on pedagogical experience, samples, methods that have proven themselves, which does not ensure the formation of readiness for independent scientific research in a developing municipal system. Approved methods and experience can become a guarantee of success if the methodologist masters the means of design technology, both his own methodological activity and the educational process. So, for example, the development of research skills and abilities of a methodologist forms his ability to identify trends in the development of education and the corresponding actual educational needs of teaching staff, to predict their dynamics, taking into account the specifics of the educational space in the system of municipal education.

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